

When ammonia addition increases the burning velocity of a fuel blend with nitromethane

Jundie Chen

Division of Combustion Physics, Lund University, SE-22100 Lund, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ammonia
Nitromethane
Laminar burning velocity
Kinetic model

ABSTRACT

Combustion properties and combustion chemistry of ammonia (NH₃) are significantly different from those of hydrocarbons and thus require further investigation. NH₃ combustion with oxidizers different from the ambient air can reveal distinct chemistry of NO_x formation, which, together with low reactivity, is one of the major obstacles in the direct deployment of ammonia as a practical fuel. In the present study, ammonia was blended with nitromethane (CH₃NO₂), which was used as a nitric oxide (NO) precursor. The laminar burning velocities (LBV) of (CH₃NO₂+NH₃)+air mixtures were investigated across a wide range of NH₃ mole fractions in the fuel blends, from 0% to 80%, spanning fuel-lean to fuel-rich conditions, at an initial temperature of 338 K and 1 atm. The results show that adding NH₃ enhances the reactivity of CH₃NO₂ when the NH₃ fraction in the fuel is below 70%. A kinetic model of the authors was updated, primarily on CH₃NO₂ chemistry, and shows very good agreement with the measurements without any rate constants tuning. Detailed kinetic analyses based on the present model reveal that the reaction NH₂+NO=NNH+OH significantly impacts the LBV even when a small portion of NH₃ is added to the fuel blend. NH₃ addition is found to increase adiabatic flame temperature and enrich the active radicals' pools of H, OH, and O as well. The pathways of NH₃ and NO interaction in (CH₃NO₂+NH₃)+air flames are also analyzed, enlightening NO conversion into N₂ in the presence of ammonia.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) has become a focal point in the efforts of energy production decarbonization due to its potential as a zero-carbon fuel. NH₃ can be produced, similar to synthesized hydrogen (H₂), from fossil fuels or using renewable energy sources. With its high volumetric hydrogen density, NH₃ is also recognized as an effective hydrogen carrier [1]. However, the direct application of ammonia as a fuel faces challenges, such as low reactivity, high ignition energy, and NO_x emissions during combustion. Therefore, extensive research has been conducted to explore the combustion of NH₃ when blended with more reactive fuels like hydrogen, hydrocarbons, or biofuels [2]. For all fuels studied so far, the laminar burning velocity (LBV) of the fuel blends decreases as the amount of NH₃ increases. For example, Lubrano Lavadera et al. [3,4] compared the effects of ammonia addition on the LBV of methane, n-heptane, isooctane, methylcyclohexane, and toluene. They observed an approximate quasi-linear monotonic decreasing correlation with the mass fraction of NH₃ in the fuel blend from 0 to 100%.

Another possibility to increase the LBV of ammonia is to modify the

oxidizer composition. Most often, the mole fraction of oxygen in (O₂+N₂) artificial air was modified, and a monotonous increase of the LBV was observed with the increase of the O₂ content in it, e.g., [5–7]. The replacement of N₂ by other inerts also affects flame propagation; for instance, the LBV of NH₃+O₂+Ar mixtures is notably higher when conditions are otherwise the same [8]. Although modifications of the oxidizer composition are less practical from the application point of view, they allow for elucidating ammonia flame chemistry at conditions vastly different from those of NH₃+air. With the same motivation, oxygen can be replaced by nitrogen oxides to isolate the impact of NH₃–NO_x interaction in flames. In the pertinent studies of the flame propagation of ammonia supported by N₂O [9] or NO [10,11], it was demonstrated that the LBV rate controlling reactions are significantly different from those for NH₃ burning in O₂, and the pathways of ammonia oxidation are also modified.

Several studies of ammonia flame propagation mentioned above [3–5,8,9] have been performed using the heat flux method at Lund University. This method is advantageous since it does not require stretch correction; however, it also possesses some limitations. Due to safety

^{*} Corresponding author at: Division of Combustion Physics, Lund University, P.O. Box 118, SE-22100, Lund, Sweden.

E-mail address: alexander.konnov@fysik.lu.se (A.A. Konnov).

concerns, stabilization of ammonia flames supported by nitric oxide is not possible; other experimental problems related to NH_3 corrosiveness and flame stability will also be discussed in the following. Zheng et al. [12] in their shock tube study proposed nitromethane (CH_3NO_2) as a nitric oxide precursor to analyze its interaction with ammonia. This suggestion is based on the stoichiometric equation for nitromethane oxidation:

Different stoichiometric equations for the oxidation of nitromethane coexist in the literature; some studies assumed that molecular nitrogen is the final product of the nitrogen atom in nitromethane. However, as discussed in previous studies of CH_3NO_2 flames [13,14] and ignition [15–17], NO should be considered instead. Simulated NO and N_2 profiles in $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + (21\% \text{O}_2 + 79\% \text{Ar})$ and $\text{NH}_3 + (21\% \text{O}_2 + 79\% \text{Ar})$ flames are provided in the Supplementary Material (SM) Fig. S1, where Ar is used instead of N_2 to eliminate the influence of atmospheric nitrogen, and fuel-lean mixtures were simulated to ensure complete fuel consumption. As shown in Fig. S1, NO is the major product of CH_3NO_2 combustion, whereas N_2 is the primary product of ammonia combustion.

Nitromethane is a green monopropellant, since it has low toxicity and relative stability compared with hydrazine and hydrazine-based propellants [18], racing fuel [19], and gasoline fuel additive [20]. Therefore, the combustion properties of CH_3NO_2 as a single fuel were investigated in a variety of studies, using different experimental or numerical methods [13–23]. In the fuel blends, nitromethane addition to CH_4 [24], gasoline [20], or syngas [25] can increase or decrease the LBV of the parent fuel, depending on the flame conditions. So far, only Zheng et al. [12] have investigated the interactions between NH_3 and CH_3NO_2 . Their shock tube study focused on NH_3 and NO chemistry, maintaining a fixed NH_3 concentration of 1% and analyzing the species profiles of NH_3 , NO, CO, and CO_2 under varying temperatures and pressures.

In the present study, the laminar burning velocities of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ blends burning in the air have been measured using the heat flux method. The NH_3 mole fraction in the fuel blends varies from 0% to 80%, covering fuel-lean to fuel-rich conditions, at a fixed initial temperature of 338 K and 1 atm. The primary objective is to investigate the interaction of NH_3 and NO, while the study also contributes to the understanding of CH_3NO_2 fuel combustion. An unexpected variation of the LBV with the addition of ammonia to the fuel blend is analysed by employing the detailed kinetic model of the authors.

2. Experimental details

2.1. Experimental methods and conditions

The LBV measurements have been performed using the heat flux method. A schematic of the setup is shown in the Supplementary Material (SM) Fig. S2. Detailed explanations of the procedures, uncertainty sources, and data processing algorithms have been given by Alekseev et al. [26]. Thus, only essential information relevant to the present experiments is introduced here.

CH_3NO_2 (purity 96%, liquid form), NH_3 (99.98% purity), and air (>99.9%) are delivered by AGA Linde Healthcare Company. The CH_3NO_2 was evaporated using a Controlled Evaporation and Mixing unit from Bronkhorst set at 200 °C. A heating hose is connected between the heat flux burner and the mixing panel to prevent possible condensation of the mixtures. The mixtures were introduced into the burner plenum chamber, which was maintained at 338 K using a water circulation system. This allows the unburnt gas to be effectively heated up to the experimental temperature of 338 K. This choice matches a prior LBV study on CH_3NO_2 and air mixtures in our laboratory to facilitate result comparison [13]. The burner head was connected to another water circulation system set at 368 K to compensate for the heat loss from the flame to the burner head, thus providing adiabatic conditions and

allowing the LBV measurements [26].

Given ammonia's corrosive nature to brass (used for all the heat flux burners in our lab), a burner called burner E2 was selected, and this burner was introduced in [26,27]. As demonstrated in [27], the measurements obtained with this burner require additional LBV uncertainty considerations due to the uncertainty in the perforated surface area of the burner plate, which will be discussed in the following section. To ensure that the burner plate's effective perforation area and performance remained unaffected by exposure to corrosive fuel, it was tested before and after the measurements with a reference gas mixture with well-documented LBV data. In this study, $\text{CH}_4 + \text{air}$ mixtures were used as references. The pre- and post-measurement results at 298 K, 1 atm aligned closely with the literature values, as shown in Fig. S3 in the SM. It is worth noting that a stainless-steel burner option was tested by Bosschaart and de Goey [28], the material of which will not be affected by ammonia corrosion. However, due to its lower thermal conductivity, stainless steel poses a risk of burner plate overheating and deformation, particularly at pressures above 200 mbar, as the flame standoff distance decreases with increasing pressure.

The data processing and uncertainty evaluations adhered to the methodology described in [26], utilizing a custom-made Matlab code. The key heat flux equation used is:

$$T_r = T_c + C * r^2 \quad (2)$$

Where T_r is the temperature at any radial distance r from the center of the burner plate. T_c is the center temperature, and C is the parabolic coefficient. The coefficient C is a crucial parameter in the heat flux method, as $C = 0$ represents the adiabatic condition with no heat transfer between the flame and the burner plate. The relationship between C and the unburnt gas inlet velocity V_g is close to linear; different V_g values were set during experiments, and corresponding C values were recorded. Extrapolating or interpolating V_g to the point where $C = 0$ yields the LBV, while interpolation is preferred due to reduced LBV determination uncertainty [26]. However, all the LBV measurements using the present burner were determined via extrapolation as exemplified in Fig. S4 in the SM. This approach was necessary because high inlet velocities led to flame corrugation, preventing a flat flame. This often happens at elevated unburned gas temperatures [26].

All the investigated mixtures are listed in Table 1. The experimental temperature was fixed at 338 K and pressure at 1 atm. It should be noted that the products of ammonia combustion are N_2 and water, as illustrated in Fig. S1 in the SM, according to

These products are also applicable for combustion in the air [1,2] and in flames supported by NO [10,11]. One may note that only Zheng et al. [12] assumed NO as a product of ammonia oxidation without reasonable arguments. For the fuel blends investigated in the present work, the equivalence ratio (Φ) was defined by combining Eq. (1) and (3). Assuming a total of 1 mol of fuel, with x mole fraction of NH_3 and $(1-x)$ mole fraction of CH_3NO_2 , then NH_3 requires $0.75x$ mol O_2 , while CH_3NO_2 requires $1.25(1-x)$ mol O_2 . Thus, the total oxygen required for stoichiometric combustion is $1.25 - 0.5x$. Thus, the global reaction for the stoichiometric combustion of the blend is:

Table 1
Investigated ($\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$)+air mixtures, at 338 K, 1 atm.

NH_3 in fuel(%)	Φ	Burner used
0	0.7–1.7	E2, E3
70	0.8–1.6	E2
0.5,10, 70, 80	1	E2
0,10,20,30,40,50,60,70	0.8	E2
0,10,20,30,40,50,60,70	0.9	E2
0,10,20,70	1.5	E2

The measurements for CH_3NO_2 +air mixtures were selectively repeated using a well-designed burner called Burner E3 [29], which normally yields results with an uncertainty of less than 0.2 cm/s [29]. An example case of the LBV determination using Burner E3 is shown in the SM Fig. S5.

2.2. Experimental uncertainty analysis

Notice that, in this work, the measurements suffer larger uncertainty bars than other results [5,8,30] from the heat flux method (normally ≤ 1 cm/s [29]). This increased uncertainty can be attributed primarily to the following factors:

- 1) The thermocouple reading scattering on the burner plate of burner E2, which is the dominant factor in overall LBV uncertainties, as analyzed by Alekseev et al. [26]. An example case of the temperature scattering from Burner E2 is depicted in the SM Fig S6(a) and compared with the temperature scattering from Burner E3 in Fig S6 (b). Moreover, it was also observed that the flames were more prone to corrugation in the present study compared to previous studies that also utilized Burner E2. A possible reason for these observations is that prolonged operation with corrosive fuels may have compromised the burner plate's attachment, reducing the heat transfer efficiency between the burner plate, the outer water circulation system, and the flame. This suboptimal heat transfer could lead to increased flame instability and affect heat transfer symmetry as discussed by Alekseev et al. [26].
- 2) NH_3 MFC calibration. Like previous experiments with NH_3 [8], the NH_3 MFC was calibrated by flowing CH_4 gas and then utilizing the conversion factors. This procedure introduces additional uncertainty in the NH_3 flow rate, thus directly affecting the equivalence ratio and total flow rate ($<2\%$, according to Bronkhorst). It is worth mentioning that the conversion factor between CH_4 and NH_3 is close to 1 (according to the Bronkhorst database), making the 2% conversion factor error a reasonable estimation.
- 3) Effective Perforation Area of Burner E2. The unclear effective perforation area of burner E2 was evaluated in the previous studies, e.g., [27], with estimated uncertainties. The present study also repeated this procedure, bringing an extra 2% error in the total flow rate.

In the end, all the LBV results and LBV uncertainties are listed in the SM Table S1. The average uncertainty in the LBV is 2 cm/s, the Φ error is less than 3.6%, and the NH_3 mole fraction has around 2% error.

3. Modeling details

3.1. Numerical method

Numerical simulations are conducted using the Premix Laminar Flame Speed code of the Chemkin Pro software, considering mixture-averaged transport and thermal diffusion. A grid-independent solution is ensured by setting the parameters GRAD and CURV to 0.02 and 0.05, resulting in a number of grid points around 500–800 over the domain of 3 cm.

3.2. Model selection

Currently, there are several kinetic models that include reactions of nitromethane pyrolysis and combustion. For instance, Mathieu et al. [31] investigated nitromethane pyrolysis in shock tubes and a microflow reactor with a controlled temperature profile. They tested the mechanisms of Brequigny et al. [32], Shrestha et al. [22], Jia et al. [33], Glarborg et al. [34], and Mathieu et al. [35]. Shang et al. [36], in turn,

measured NO time-histories during nitromethane pyrolysis in a shock tube and compared their experiments with predictions of the models by Gao et al. [16], Weng et al. [37] and Shang et al. [38]; they found that the latter model is in the best agreement with their measurements. In the recent experimental and modeling study of nitromethane ignition in a shock tube, Zhang et al. [39] tested NUIGMech 1.3 [40] and kinetic models of Glarborg et al. [34], Brequigny et al. [32], Mathieu et al. [15], and Weng et al. [37].

Many of the models mentioned above [16,36–39] or suggested recently [15,41–43] have been developed and validated using 0D experimental data, such as ignition delays or speciation in flow and well-stirred reactors; hence they do not include transport properties of the pertinent species and cannot be used for flame modeling. The models of Brequigny et al. [32] and Mathieu et al. [15] have been tested against the LBV measurements by Brackmann et al. [14], where good agreement was found for the latter mechanism. A comprehensive mechanism presented by Glarborg et al. [34] was found, e.g., by Alnasif et al. [44], too reactive in predicting LBV of NH_3 +air and (NH_3+H_2) +air flames, for which the model of Shrestha et al. [7] demonstrated good performance. Shrestha et al. [22] concluded that their model correctly reproduces LBV measurements in CH_3NO_2 +air flames obtained by Brequigny et al. [32] at 423 K and pressures from 1 to 3 atm. Therefore, in the present study, the models of Mathieu et al. [38], the recent model of Shrestha et al. [45], and the model of the authors are compared and analyzed. It should be noted that the original mechanism from Mathieu et al. [15] did not include transport properties, which were incorporated by Brackmann et al. [14] from Aramco 2.0 mech and the earlier version of the Konnov mechanism [46]. In the present work, these transport properties have not been updated.

3.3. The present model

Glarborg et al. [47] emphasized the role of the CH_3+NO_2 reaction in the promotion of fuel oxidation by small amounts of nitrogen oxides. Although sensitization reactions of hydrocarbons oxidation by nitrogen oxides were implemented in the Konnov mechanism version 0.6 [48] as discussed in pertinent studies, e.g., [49,50], a complete nitromethane combustion sub-mechanism was not developed at that time. Therefore, no attempts were made to compare its performance with the measured burning velocities [13,14] or ignition delays [17].

The starting mechanism for the present model is taken from [51] for hydrocarbons, with the latest updated NH_3 sub-mechanism adopted from [5,52]; both are from the authors' previous works. Nitromethane combustion modeling required the introduction of reactions of CH_3NO_2 , CH_2NO_2 , methyl-nitrite, CH_3ONO , and hydrogen isocyanide, HNC, following the suggestions of Glarborg et al. [47]. The thermodynamic data for these species were taken from the Burcat database [53]. The choice of the rate constants of these reactions is outlined in the SM. The rate constant expressions in the present model are based on experimental, theoretical, or review data, and there has been no modification (adjustment or tuning) of the values to accommodate experimental results. Rate constants have units of $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$, and the activation energies are in cal/mol.

Several rate constants not relevant to nitromethane have also been modified in the present work. These rate constants originate from theoretical studies where sometimes rate expressions are presented in PLOG format with one positive and one negative term to better approximate their temperature variation at a specific pressure. These expressions cause convergence problems in flame modeling, especially with the Cantera collection of codes [54]. Therefore, they were recalculated and replaced by the expressions consisting of two strictly positive terms, as detailed in the SM Section S3.

4. Results and analysis

4.1. Experimental and modeling results

Fig. 1 shows the LBV of pure CH_3NO_2 +air mixtures from the present study and Naucler et al. [13]. The LBV data from Burners E2 and E3 in the present study agree within the uncertainty range. The results from Burner E2 have larger error bars, especially when $\Phi \geq 1$. Both the present model and the model of Mathieu et al. [15] provide very good predictions, while the model of Shrestha et al. [45] under-predicts the flame reactivity across the entire equivalence ratio range.

The data from Naucler et al. [13] were adjusted by multiplying by a factor of 1.023, as suggested by Alekseev et al. [26], due to inaccuracies in the burner's surface area; Alekseev et al. [26] reported that the actual surface area of the burner is 1.023 times smaller than the value used by Naucler et al. [13]. As a result, the corrected flow rate and LBV should be 1.023 times higher to reflect the true conditions. Despite this, Alekseev et al. [26] raised concerns about a potential LBV underestimation of 1–3 cm/s. Our recent study [30] confirmed that the LBV data remain lower even after applying the factor, recommending the exclusion of the data obtained by this specific burner from future model validations. Another study by Brequigny et al. [31] also provided LBVs of CH_3NO_2 +air mixtures, but their results are not included for comparison, due to concerns about their data accuracy, as discussed by Naucler et al. [13] and Faghiih and Chen [21].

Fig. 2 shows the LBV with four equivalence ratios fixed at $\Phi = 0.8, 0.9, 1.0,$ and 1.5 , while the NH_3 mole fraction in the fuel ($\text{NH}_3\%$) varies from 0% to 100%. The limitation in the investigation range is associated with the burner used in this study, as previous experiments utilizing a different burner successfully explored flame speeds in the range of 15–60 cm/s [5,8]. The current limitation may be attributed to deteriorated burner performance resulting from prolonged operation with corrosive fuels. As discussed earlier, flames in this study tended to become corrugated at high inlet velocities of unburnt gas. Consequently, laminar burning velocities (LBVs) could only be determined via extrapolation from lower inlet velocities, where the flames remained flat and stable.

Under these conditions ($V_g < \text{LBV}$), the flame becomes closely attached to the burner plate, resulting in elevated burner plate

Fig. 1. Experimental (symbols) and simulated (lines) LBV of CH_3NO_2 +air flames. Solid line: the present model, dashed line: the model of Mathieu et al. [15], dotted line: the model of Shrestha et al. [45].

Fig. 2. Experimental (symbols) and simulated (lines) LBV of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{NH}_3)$ +air mixtures with various $\text{NH}_3\%$ in the fuel, at $\Phi = 0.8, 0.9, 1.0,$ and 1.5 . Solid lines: the present model, dashed lines: the model of Mathieu et al. [15], dotted lines: the model of Shrestha et al. [45].

temperatures. This poses a risk of melting the thermal paste between the burner plate and the burner head. Based on our experience, we therefore limited the burner plate temperature to below 180°C during experiments to prevent any damage. As a result, the upper range of LBVs that could be investigated was restricted, since flames with higher LBVs cause higher burner plate temperatures. The deteriorated burner performance is most likely attributed to ineffective heat transfer within the burner plate, as previously discussed in the Experimental Uncertainties section. This issue was caused by a compromised attachment between the burner plate and the burner head, leading to heat accumulation and a rise in temperature within the plate. The lower LBV limit was set by flame instability; when LBV falls below 24 cm/s, the flames become weak and tremble.

In Fig. 2, the LBV of the mixture follows a parabolic-like trend with respect to $\text{NH}_3\%$, a behavior that remains consistent across all tested equivalence ratios. As $\text{NH}_3\%$ in the fuel blend increases, the LBV initially rises, reaching a maximum at around 40% NH_3 , and then decreases. Thus, the $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{NH}_3$ mixtures constitute an unexpected and unique case when ammonia addition increases the burning velocity of a fuel blend contrary to all previously studied mixtures with H_2 , hydrocarbons or biofuels mentioned in the Introduction. The only exception to this behaviour was demonstrated and discussed by Wang et al. [55]. The authors found in the experimental study and modeling that for the fuel blend of NH_3+CO small addition of ammonia increases LBV. This is not surprising since it is well known that dry $\text{CO}+\text{air}$ mixtures have very low LBV, while the addition of hydrogen in any form, even as H_2O increases it by activating the chain-branching reaction $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{O}$.

Both the present model and the model of Mathieu et al. [15] predict LBV data well when NH_3 is present in the fuel. However, these two models show slight discrepancies, especially when the $\text{NH}_3\%$ exceeds around 70%, with the Mathieu model predicting lower LBV values than the present model. The Shrestha model under-predicts the LBV of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{NH}_3)$ +air mixtures when $\text{NH}_3\%$ is below approximately 30% but performs better as $\text{NH}_3\%$ increases.

To explore the LBV of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{NH}_3)$ +air mixtures over a wider equivalence ratio range, a fuel mixture with 70% NH_3 was chosen. Fig. 3 shows the LBV of $(30\% \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + 70\% \text{NH}_3)$ +air mixtures. The present

Fig. 3. Experimental (symbols) and simulated (lines) LBV of (30% CH_3NO_2 +70% NH_3)+air mixtures. Solid line: the present model, dashed line: the model of Mathieu et al. [15], dotted line: the model of Shrestha et al. [45].

model and the model of Mathieu et al. [15] predict the LBV accurately across the entire equivalence ratio range, while the model of Shrestha et al. [45] notably over-predicts the LBV on the fuel-rich side.

In summary, both the present model and the model of Mathieu et al. [15] match the LBV of the investigated mixtures well, but the model of Shrestha et al. [45] failed to reproduce measurements, especially when CH_3NO_2 is the major fuel in the blends. The model of Mathieu et al. [15] under-predicts the flame reactivity when NH_3 is the major fuel, as will be discussed in Section 5, where it severely under-predicts the LBV of NH_3 +NO mixtures.

The present model, being the latest version from the author's group with updated kinetic reactions, will be used for further analysis, while the kinetic analyses using another two models will only be included in the SM for comparison.

4.2. Kinetic analyses

To investigate the enhancing effect of NH_3 on the LBV of the blends studied, kinetic analyses were performed. The analysis initially focused on stoichiometric mixtures to eliminate the influence of equivalence ratio. Tools such as sensitivity analysis, reaction pathway analysis, and species mole fraction analysis were employed, as described below. Together, these methods provide a comprehensive understanding of the ammonia and nitromethane synergy in flame propagation.

The adiabatic flame temperature (T_{ad}) is the dominant factor affecting LBV. Since it is known that NH_3 flames are characterized by lower T_{ad} compared to hydrocarbon flames, it is interesting to see if the promoting effect of NH_3 on the LBV of CH_3NO_2 can be correlated to a variation of T_{ad} . In Fig. 4, $T_{\text{ad},0}$ and LBV_0 denote the adiabatic flame temperature and the LBV of the CH_3NO_2 +air mixture, while T_{ad} and LBV represent corresponding parameters with NH_3 addition in the fuel blend. As can be seen in Fig. 4, when $\text{NH}_3\%$ is below about 70%, the ratios $T_{\text{ad}}/T_{\text{ad},0}$ and LBV/LBV_0 both exceed 1, indicating that NH_3 enhances both the flame temperature and the LBV. With around 40% NH_3 in the fuel, both $T_{\text{ad}}/T_{\text{ad},0}$ and LBV/LBV_0 reach their peak values.

As CH_3NO_2 is a precursor of NO [12], it is expected that blending NH_3 with CH_3NO_2 induces reactions between NH_3 and NO formed during CH_3NO_2 decomposition. These reactions release additional heat and enhance LBV. To validate this hypothesis, first, sensitivity analysis of the

Fig. 4. $T_{\text{ad}}/T_{\text{ad},0}$ (left y-axis) and LBV/LBV_0 (right y-axis) as a function of $\text{NH}_3\%$ at $\Phi=1$.

LBV was performed under stoichiometric conditions, with 0%, 10%, 40%, and 80% NH_3 in the fuel blends, as shown in Fig. 5. Reactions with positive sensitivity coefficients promote LBV when increasing their rate, while reactions with negative sensitivity coefficients inhibit LBV when increasing their rate. Sensitivity analyses using the Mathieu model [15] and Shrestha model [45] at corresponding conditions are shown in the SM Fig S9.

The chain branching reaction $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{H}$ is always the most sensitive reaction in all fuel blends. For CH_3NO_2 +air mixtures, reactions involving species of CO, HCO, and CH_3O are crucial. Reaction $\text{CO} + \text{OH} = \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ plays a dominant LBV promoting roles, followed H/HO_2 producing reactions $\text{HCO} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO} + \text{HO}_2$, $\text{HCO} (+\text{M}) = \text{H} + \text{CO} (+\text{M})$, $\text{CH}_3\text{O} (+\text{M}) = \text{CH}_2\text{O} + \text{H} (+\text{M})$. OH producing reaction $\text{NO} + \text{HO}_2 = \text{NO}_2 + \text{OH}$ is also reactivity-promoting, followed by NO producing reaction $\text{CH}_3 + \text{NO}_2 = \text{CH}_3\text{O} + \text{NO}$. Conversely, reactions consuming NO, such as $\text{HCO} + \text{NO} = \text{HNO} + \text{CO}$, $\text{NO} + \text{O} (+\text{M}) = \text{NO}_2 (+\text{M})$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{O} + \text{NO} = \text{HNO} + \text{CH}_2\text{O}$, exhibit inhibitory effects on flame reactivity, since they compete with $\text{NO} + \text{HO}_2 = \text{NO}_2 + \text{OH}$. The bond scission reaction $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 (+\text{M}) = \text{CH}_3 + \text{NO}_2 (+\text{M})$ produces CH_3 and NO_2 , which act as key fuel and oxidizer intermediates, thus also showing strong sensitivity.

As the $\text{NH}_3\%$ increases, NH_3 -related oxidation chemistry becomes increasingly significant, ultimately dominating the overall reactivity at 80% NH_3 , as shown by the green bars in Fig. 5, which highlight reactions sensitive to NH_3 oxidation discussed elsewhere [1]. Interestingly, even with only 10% NH_3 in the fuel, the sensitivity coefficient of $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ becomes significant. Furthermore, the reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$, typically a reactivity-inhibiting reaction in NH_3 flames [8], enhances flame reactivity in $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3$ flames when $\text{NH}_3\%$ is below 80%. Generally speaking, the addition of ammonia to the fuel blend converts part of the NO formed in nitromethane oxidation, producing N_2 that, in turn, leads to supplementary heat release. It can also be observed that the sensitivities of several reactions change significantly with increasing NH_3 , for example, the sensitivity of the $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{O}$ reaction decreases at 10% and 40% NH_3 due to the contribution of $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$, which also produces OH. However, at 80% NH_3 , NH_3 -related oxidation chemistry dominates the reactivity where $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{O}$ regains its dominance, consistent with typical NH_3 combustion behavior. Additionally, the reactions $\text{HCO} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{H} = \text{N}_2 + \text{OH}$ exhibit a reversal in sensitivity sign, switching from promoting to inhibiting at 80% NH_3 . This change can be attributed to their competition with $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{O}$, which becomes increasingly dominant at high NH_3 content. The bond scission reaction $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 (+\text{M}) = \text{CH}_3 + \text{NO}_2 (+\text{M})$ becomes less important when 80% NH_3 is present in the fuel, likely due to the rising

Fig. 5. Sensitivity spectra for $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{NH}_3)+\text{air}$ flames, at stoichiometric conditions, 338 K, 1 atm, $\Phi=1$.

dominance of the rate-controlling reactions from NH_3 oxidation chemistry.

Sensitivity analyses using the model of Mathieu et al. [15] and the model of Shrestha et al. [45] under stoichiometric conditions with 0%, 40%, and 80% NH_3 in the fuel blends are presented in the SM Fig. S9. Compared to the present model (Fig. 5), the Mathieu model shows similar dominant reactions for pure CH_3NO_2 mixtures. In both cases, $\text{HCO} + \text{NO} = \text{HNO} + \text{CO}$ appears as the dominant inhibiting reaction, while $\text{CO} + \text{OH} = \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ is the dominant promoting reaction. Other important reactions are also the same as in the present model, including $\text{CH}_3 + \text{H} (+\text{M}) = \text{CH}_4 (+\text{M})$, $\text{HCO} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO} + \text{HO}_2$, the CH_3NO_2 decomposition reaction, and $\text{HCO} + \text{M} = \text{H} + \text{CO} + \text{M}$.

In contrast, the Shrestha model displays a different sensitivity spectrum for CH_3NO_2 mixtures. In this model, $\text{CH}_3 + \text{H} (+\text{M}) = \text{CH}_4 (+\text{M})$ and $\text{NO} + \text{H} (+\text{M}) = \text{HNO} (+\text{M})$ are the most inhibiting reactions, while $\text{HCO} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO} + \text{HO}_2$ is not significant. When NH_3 content increases to 80%, the discrepancies between the present model and the Mathieu model become more apparent. While both models show strong sensitivity to $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ and $\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ reactions, the present model identifies $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NH} = \text{tHNNH} + \text{H}$ as a key reaction, consistent with our previous NH_3 flame studies [5,8]. In contrast, the Mathieu model does not consider HNNH-related reactions to be significant; instead, it emphasizes only NNH-related pathways. These NNH reactions are far less prominent in the present model. Interestingly, the Shrestha model shows a sensitivity spectrum more consistent with the present model at high NH_3 blending ratios.

This comparison may help explain the differences in model predictions. The present model aligns more closely with the Mathieu model when CH_3NO_2 is the dominant fuel component, due to the similarity in CH_3NO_2 chemistry. However, as NH_3 becomes the primary fuel, greater discrepancies emerge. In contrast, the Shrestha model appears to better match the present model under high NH_3 content conditions.

Sensitivity analysis at equivalence ratios $\Phi = 0.8$ and 1.5, with 0%, 40%, and 80% NH_3 addition, are presented in the SM Fig. S10. Compared to stoichiometric conditions, the sensitivity spectra at $\Phi = 0.8$ and 1.5 display similar dominant reactions but with varying sensitivity coefficients and are therefore not detailed here. As in the stoichiometric case, under both fuel-lean and rich conditions, reactions $\text{CO} + \text{OH} = \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}$ and $\text{HCO} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO} + \text{HO}_2$ play key roles in promoting reactivity when CH_3NO_2 constitutes a large proportion of the fuel blends; while reaction $\text{HCO} + \text{NO} = \text{HNO} + \text{CO}$ is the most reactivity inhibiting reaction. The reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ consistently emerges as a major promoter of reactivity with NH_3 addition to the fuel.

The major reaction pathways for CH_3NO_2 and NH_3 at $\Phi=1$ for various NH_3 blending ratios are illustrated in Fig. 6, based on the rate of production (ROP) analysis from Chemkin Pro. The underlined numbers next to the arrows represent the percentage of reactant species converted into product species, through reactions with the species next to the arrows. These percentages are calculated by dividing the rate of consumption (i. e., the negative ROP values) of the reactant via a specific reaction pathway by the total consumption rate of that reactant. Black arrows and numbers denote pathways and flux percentages for $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{air}$ flame, while blue dashed arrows show flux for 40% (with red numbers) and 80% NH_3 (with green numbers) fuel blends. It is worth noting that NH_3 consumption pathways also appear in the CH_3NO_2 and air flame; however, the ROP values of the species in NH_3 oxidation chemistry are close to zero, therefore, the flux percentages are not shown in the pure CH_3NO_2 case.

In $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{air}$ flames, the primary carbon pathway from CH_3NO_2 to CO_2 is as follows: $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$. This aligns with Fig. 5, which highlights the importance of reactions involving CH_3O , CH_2O , HCO , CO , and the reaction of the bond scission of nitromethane $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2(+\text{M}) = \text{CH}_3 + \text{NO}_2(+\text{M})$. The nitrogen atom in CH_3NO_2 primarily converts to NO via a shorter pathway: $\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO}$. The NO formed participates in oxidation pathways, such as the conversion of CH_3O to CH_2O through the reaction $\text{CH}_3\text{O} + \text{NO} = \text{CH}_2\text{O} + \text{HNO}$ and the conversion of HCO to CO through $\text{HCO} + \text{NO} = \text{HNO} + \text{CO}$. NO is also converted back to NO_2 through reactions of $\text{NO} + \text{O} (+\text{M}) = \text{NO}_2 (+\text{M})$ and $\text{NO} + \text{HO}_2 = \text{NO}_2 + \text{OH}$.

With 40% NH_3 in the fuel blend, as illustrated by the blue pathways and red numbers, the NH_3 oxidation pathway appears: $\text{NH}_3 \rightarrow \text{NH}_2 \rightarrow \text{NNH} \rightarrow \text{N}_2$. Nearly all NH_3 converts to NH_2 , which will react directly with NO that is produced from CH_3NO_2 through reactions $\text{NO} + \text{NH}_2 = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ (18%) and $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (23%). Consequently, NO consumption pathways participated in $\text{CH}_3\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{CO}$ in the neat nitromethane flame diminished to 11% and 14%, respectively. These pathways, which inhibit flame reactivity, become less prominent, as manifested in Fig. 5.

At 80% NH_3 , more NH_2 radicals convert into NH (31%), as NO from CH_3NO_2 decreases, reducing participation in $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (12%) and $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ (10%), as illustrated by the green numbers. Reactions of NH_3 chemistry dominate, and the lower reactivity of NH_3 reduces LBV for blends with further increasing $\text{NH}_3\%$.

Fig. 7 shows the maximum mole fractions of the key species (OH , H , O , NO , NH_2) as a function of $\text{NH}_3\%$. NO decreases consistently with NH_3 addition, contrasting with NH_2 . The maximum OH and O concentration

Fig. 6. Species reaction pathways at $\Phi=1$. Black numbers: 0% NH_3 ; Red numbers: 40% NH_3 ; Green numbers: 80% NH_3 .

Fig. 7. Maximum mole fraction values of critical species in stoichiometric $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2+\text{NH}_3)$ +air flames as NH_3 % in the fuel increases.

occurs at 40–60% NH_3 . A rate-of-production (ROP) analysis for OH in the mixtures with 0%, 40%, and 80% NH_3 in the fuel blends shown in the SM Fig. S11 reveals that $\text{NO}_2 + \text{H} = \text{NO} + \text{OH}$ and $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{O}$ are the primary OH-producing reactions. At 40% NH_3 , both pathways are highly effective. This suggests that at this NH_3 proportion, NO_2 derived from the decomposition of CH_3NO_2 are still in a good amount to support $\text{NO}_2 + \text{H} = \text{NO} + \text{OH}$ reaction. At the same time, as NO from CH_3NO_2 works as an effective oxidizer in the NH_3 oxidation pathways (Fig. 6), providing more opportunities for the supplied O_2 in the oxidizer to react with H, thereby enhancing the reaction $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{OH} + \text{O}$.

5. Additional validation of the models

Most recently, Monnier et al. [11] experimentally investigated the laminar burning velocity of $\text{NH}_3 + (\text{NO} + \text{N}_2)$ mixtures. Since this work is closely related to the present study, the models tested here were evaluated against their experimental results. Fig. 8 illustrates the predictions of the present model, the models by Mathieu et al. [15] and Shrestha et al. [45], compared with the measurements of Monnier et al. [11]. The NO proportion in the oxidizer ($\text{NO} + \text{N}_2$) varies from 40% to 70%, at the initial temperature of 298 K and pressure of 1 atm.

In Fig. 8, the model by Mathieu et al. [15] poorly predicts the LBV of $\text{NH}_3 + (\text{NO} + \text{N}_2)$ mixtures; the model of Shrestha et al. [45] over-predicts the LBV for mixtures with 40% and 50% NO in the oxidizer, especially on the fuel-rich side. The performance of the present model varies across different NO percentages and equivalence ratios. It generally provides good predictions but under-predicts LBV on the fuel-lean side with 70% NO in the oxidizer, and over-predicts LBV on the fuel-lean side for 50% NO in the oxidizer. Remarkably, all the most recent kinetic models tested in Monnier et al. [11] showed over-predictions for 50% NO series. It could be noted that the model by Han et al. [9] performed the best in the study by Monnier et al. [11], and was the base model for the present N/H/O sub-mechanism, developed by the authors' group.

Figure S12 in the SM presents sensitivity analysis for 50% and 70% NO mixtures under fuel-lean ($\Phi = 0.8$) and fuel-rich ($\Phi = 1.6$) conditions. The reactions $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ and $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ demonstrate extraordinarily high sensitivity for the LBV predictions, regardless of NO percentage or equivalence ratio. The reaction

$\text{N} + \text{OH} = \text{NO} + \text{H}$ also shows a strong promoting effect under fuel-lean conditions. This agrees with analysis by Monnier et al. [11], since these most sensitive reactions have the same directional impact on LBV, however, it remains unclear why the model predictions are generally in good agreement but show over-predictions on the fuel-lean side with 50% NO and under-predictions with 70% NO.

Other reactions with minor sensitivity coefficients were reviewed, focusing on those that showed differing sensitivity coefficients for 50% and 70% NO on the fuel-lean side. However, most of these reactions were revisited and selected in our recent paper [5], with their rate constants adopted from the latest theoretical studies. For example, the rate constants for reactions $\text{HNO} + \text{H} = \text{NO} + \text{H}_2$ and $\text{NH} + \text{OH} = \text{HNO} + \text{H}$ were adopted from Klippenstein et al. [56], while for $\text{NH}_2 + \text{H} = \text{NH} + \text{H}_2$ was taken from Li and Sarathy [57]. The reaction $\text{NNH} + \text{H} = \text{N}_2 + \text{H}$ was adopted from theoretical calculations by Klippenstein et al. [58], which choice was noted in [5] for further analysis. If the experimental data and their uncertainty ranges in Monnier et al. [11] are trustworthy, these reactions should be further studied in the future with dedicated work. For now, they will be retained as is, without being tuned to match the experimental results.

6. Conclusions

In this work, laminar burning velocities of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3) + \text{air}$ mixtures are investigated for the first time. The NH_3 proportion in the fuel ($\text{NH}_3\%$) varies from 0% to 80%, with equivalence ratios varying from fuel-lean side to fuel-rich side, at a fixed experimental temperature of 338 K and pressure of 1 atm. The promoting effect of NH_3 on the LBV of CH_3NO_2 was observed when the NH_3 proportion was below around 70% in the fuel, and the maximum promoting effect was found at 40% NH_3 .

An updated model based on previous iterations of the authors was proposed and compared against the present LBV measurements, together with the models of Mathieu et al. [15] and Shrestha et al. [45]. It was found that both the present and the model of Mathieu et al. [15] give very good predictions for the present $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3) + \text{air}$ flames.

The present model was employed for kinetic analysis, revealing that the reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ plays a dominant role in influencing the LBV with NH_3 addition. Flux analysis confirmed that interactions between NH_3 and CH_3NO_2 occur primarily through reactions of NH_2 radicals with NO, which is directly produced from CH_3NO_2 . The highest concentrations of free radicals (H, O, OH) were observed at approximately 40% NH_3 . Rate-of-production (ROP) analysis showed that OH radicals are predominantly formed through the reactions $\text{H} + \text{O}_2 = \text{O} + \text{OH}$ and $\text{NO}_2 + \text{H} = \text{NO} + \text{OH}$, both of which are significantly promoted at 40% NH_3 addition.

Novelty and significance statement

The present study, for the first time, investigated the LBV of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 + \text{NH}_3) + \text{air}$ mixtures. Unlike the inhibiting effect of NH_3 on hydrocarbon fuels, a promoting effect was observed with the addition of NH_3 to CH_3NO_2 fuel. This effect was found to result from the interaction between NH_3 and NO through the reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} = \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$. The present study also introduces an updated kinetic model, based on iterative versions developed by the authors, which accurately predicts the LBV of the investigated fuel blends. Hence, this work contributes to the development of CH_3NO_2 chemistry and provides valuable insights into $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ interaction.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jundie Chen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Alexander A. Konnov:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Fig. 8. Experimental (symbols) and simulated (lines) LBV of $\text{NH}_3 + (\text{NO} + \text{N}_2)$ mixtures. Experiments are from [11]. Solid lines: the present model, dashed lines: the model of Mathieu et al. [15], dotted lines: the model of Shrestha et al. [45].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation through grant KAW2019.0084 COCALD and by the European Union Project CAIPIRINH₃A, under the GA number 101191768. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2025.114230](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2025.114230).

References

- M. Monge-Palacios, X. Zhang, N. Morlanes, H. Nakamura, G. Pezzella, S. M. Sarathy, Ammonia pyrolysis and oxidation chemistry, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 105 (2024) 101177.
- L. Kang, W. Pan, J. Zhang, W. Wang, C. Tang, A review on ammonia blends combustion for industrial applications, *Fuel* 332 (2023) 126150.
- M. Lubrano Lavadera, X. Han, A.A. Konnov, Comparative effect of Ammonia addition on the laminar burning velocities of methane, n-heptane, and iso-octane, *Energy Fuels* 35 (2020) 7156–7168.
- M. Lubrano Lavadera, M. Pelucchi, A.A. Konnov, The influence of ammonia on the laminar burning velocities of methylcyclohexane and toluene: an experimental and kinetic modeling study, *Combust. Flame* 237 (2022) 111839.
- J. Chen, X. Han, A.A. Konnov, Data consistency of the laminar burning velocity of oxygen-enriched NH₃ + O₂ + N₂ mixtures and kinetic modeling, *Fuel* 385 (2025) 134017.
- X. Han, H. Feng, R. Lin, A.A. Konnov, A new correlation between diluent fraction and laminar burning velocities: example of CH₄, NH₃, and CH₄ + NH₃ flames diluted by N₂, *Fuel* 364 (2024) 131108.
- K.P. Shrestha, C. Lhuillier, A.A. Barbosa, P. Brequigny, F. Contino, C. Mounaïm-Rousselle, L. Seidel, F. Mauss, An experimental and modeling study of ammonia with enriched oxygen content and ammonia/hydrogen laminar flame speed at elevated pressure and temperature, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 2163–2174.
- J. Chen, M. Lubrano Lavadera, A.A. Konnov, An experimental and modeling study on the laminar burning velocities of ammonia+oxygen+argon mixtures, *Combust. Flame* 255 (2023) 112930.
- X. Han, M. Lubrano Lavadera, A.A. Konnov, An experimental and kinetic modeling study on the laminar burning velocity of NH₃+N₂O+air flames, *Combust. Flame* 228 (2021) 13–28.
- B. Mei, S. Ma, X. Zhang, Y. Li, Characterizing ammonia and nitric oxide interaction with outwardly propagating spherical flame method, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 2477–2485.
- N. Monnier, N. Lamoureux, S. Zitouni, P. Brequigny, C. Mounaïm-Rousselle, Laminar burning velocity of NH₃/NO/N₂ mixtures: an experimental and numerical study, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 40 (2024) 105266.
- D. Zheng, D. He, Y. Du, Y. Ding, Z. Peng, Nitromethane as a nitric oxide precursor for studying high-temperature interactions between ammonia and nitric oxide in a shock tube, *Combust. Flame* 250 (2023) 112644.
- J.D. Naucler, E.J.K. Nilsson, A.A. Konnov, Laminar burning velocity of nitromethane + air flames: a comparison of flat and spherical flames, *Combust. Flame* 162 (2015) 3803–3809.
- C. Brackmann, J.D. Naucler, S. El-Busaidy, A. Hosseinnia, P.-E. Bengtsson, A. A. Konnov, E.J.K. Nilsson, Experimental studies of nitromethane flames and evaluation of kinetic mechanisms, *Combust. Flame* 190 (2018) 327–336.
- O. Mathieu, B. Giri, A.R. Agard, T.N. Adams, J.D. Mertens, E.L. Petersen, Nitromethane ignition behind reflected shock waves: experimental and numerical study, *Fuel* 182 (2016) 597–612.
- Z. Gao, M. Yang, C. Tang, F. Yang, K. Yang, F. Deng, Z. Huang, Measurements of the high temperature ignition delay times and kinetic modeling study on oxidation of nitromethane, *Combust. Sci. Technol.* 192 (2020) 313–334.
- J.D. Naucler, Y. Li, E.J.K. Nilsson, H.J. Curran, A.A. Konnov, An experimental and modeling study of nitromethane + O₂ + N₂ ignition in a shock tube, *Fuel* 186 (2016) 629–638.
- R.A. Schwind, J.B. Sinrud, C.C. Fuller, M.S. Klassen, R.A. Walker, C.F. Goldsmith, Experimental study of linear burning rates of liquid nitromethane using a novel high-pressure continuous feed liquid strand burner, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 39 (2023) 5083–5090.
- E.S. Starkman, Nitroparaffins as potential engine fuel, *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 51 (1959) 1477–1480.
- S. Raviteja, P.A. Ramakrishna, A. Ramesh, Laminar burning speeds of nitromethane-gasoline blends at elevated temperatures and pressures, *J. Energy Resour. Technol.* 141 (2019) 042202.
- M. Faghih, Z. Chen, Two-stage heat release in nitromethane/air flame and its impact on laminar flame speed measurement, *Combust. Flame* 183 (2017) 157–165.
- K.P. Shrestha, N. Vin, O. Herbinet, L. Seidel, F. Battin-Leclerc, T. Zeuch, F. Mauss, Insights into nitromethane combustion from detailed kinetic modeling – Pyrolysis experiments in jet-stirred and flow reactors, *Fuel* 261 (2020) 116349.
- M. Yang, Z. Gao, C. Tang, Z. Xu, Z. Gao, E. Hu, Z. Huang, Nitromethane pyrolysis and oxidation in a jet-stirred reactor: experimental measurements, kinetic model validation and interpretation, *Fuel* 263 (2020) 116491.
- I. Fells, A.G. Rutherford, Burning velocity of methane-air flames, *Combust. Flame* 13 (1969) 130–138.
- A. Bhattacharya, A. Datta, Effects of nitromethane addition on the laminar burning velocity and ignition delay of syngas/air flames, *Combust. Sci. Technol.* 190 (2018) 1283–1301.
- V.A. Alekseev, J.D. Naucler, M. Christensen, E.J.K. Nilsson, E.N. Volkov, L.P.H. de Goey, A.A. Konnov, Experimental uncertainties of the heat flux method for measuring burning velocities, *Combust. Sci. Technol.* 188 (2016) 853–894.
- M. Lubrano Lavadera, J. Chen, A.A. Konnov, Laminar burning velocities of pyrrole/air flames: experimental and comprehensive modeling study, *Combust. Flame* 245 (2022) 112350.
- K.J. Bosschaert, L.P.H. de Goey, Extension of the heat flux method to subatmospheric pressures, *Combust. Sci. Technol.* 176 (2004) 1537–1564.
- M. Lubrano Lavadera, A.A. Konnov, Data consistency of the burning velocity measurements using the heat flux method: syngas flames, *Energy Fuels* 34 (2020) 3725–3742.
- A.A. Konnov, J. Chen, M. Lubrano Lavadera, Measurements of the laminar burning velocities of small alkyl esters using the heat flux method: a comparative study, *Combust. Flame* 255 (2023) 112922.
- O. Mathieu, N. Chaumeix, Y. Yamamoto, S. Abid, C.-E. Paillard, T. Tezuka, H. Nakamura, C.R. Mulvihill, E.L. Petersen, Nitromethane pyrolysis in shock tubes and a micro flow reactor with a controlled temperature profile, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 1007–1015.
- P. Brequigny, G. Dayma, F. Halter, C. Mounaïm-Rousselle, T. Dubois, P. Dagaut, Laminar burning velocities of premixed nitromethane/air flames: an experimental and kinetic modeling study, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 35 (2015) 703–710.
- Z. Jia, Z. Wang, Z. Cheng, W. Zhou, Experimental and modeling study on pyrolysis of n-decane initiated by nitromethane, *Combust. Flame* 165 (2016) 246–258.
- P. Glarborg, J.A. Miller, B. Ruscic, S.J. Klippenstein, Modeling nitrogen chemistry in combustion, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 67 (2018) 31–68.
- O. Mathieu, C.R. Mulvihill, E.L. Petersen, Assessment of modern detailed kinetics mechanisms to predict CO formation from methane combustion using shock-tube laser-absorption measurements, *Fuel* 236 (2019) 1164–1180.
- Y. Shang, Z. Wang, L. Ma, J. Shi, H. Ning, W. Ren, S.-N. Luo, Shock tube measurement of NO time-histories in nitromethane pyrolysis using a quantum cascade laser at 5.26 μm, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 1745–1752.
- J.-J. Weng, Z.-Y. Tian, K.-W. Zhang, L.-L. Ye, Y.-X. Liu, L.-N. Wu, D. Yu, J.-Z. Yang, C.-C. Cao, J.-B. Zou, Experimental and kinetic investigation of pyrolysis and oxidation of nitromethane, *Combust. Flame* 203 (2019) 247–254.
- Y. Shang, J. Shi, H. Ning, R. Zhang, S.-N. Luo, Significance of reaction CH₃+NO=H₂CN+OH in two-stage ignition of nitromethane, *Fuel* 256 (2019) 115956.
- Y. Zhang, Z. Zhao, R. Ma, J. Liang, Q. Yao, Q.-D. Wang, F. Zhao, Experimental and modeling study on the ignition kinetics of nitromethane behind reflected shock waves, *ACS. Omega* 8 (2023) 39749–39758.
- A.A.E.-S. Mohamed, A.B. Sahu, S. Panigrahy, M. Baigomhamadi, G. Bourque, H. Curran, The effect of the addition of nitrogen oxides on the oxidation of propane: an experimental and modeling study, *Combust. Flame* 245 (2022) 112306.
- Z. Sun, Y. Deng, S. Song, J. Yang, W. Yuan, F. Qi, Experimental and kinetic modeling study of the homogeneous chemistry of NH₃ and NO_x with CH₄ at the diluted conditions, *Combust. Flame* 243 (2022) 112015.
- Y. Shang, J. Shi, H. Ning, R. Zhang, H. Wang, S. Luo, Ignition delay time measurements and kinetic modeling of CH₄ initiated by CH₃NO₂, *Fuel* 243 (2019) 288–297.
- Y. Shang, J. Shi, H. Ning, R. Zhang, S.-N. Luo, Abnormal promotion effect of nitromethane on ethane ignition, *Combust. Flame* 223 (2021) 267–270.
- A. Alnasif, S. Mashruk, H. Shi, M. Alnajideen, P. Wang, D. Pugh, A. Valera-Medina, Evolution of ammonia reaction mechanisms and modeling parameters: a review, *Appl. Energy Combust. Sci.* 15 (2023) 100175.
- K.P. Shrestha, L. Seidel, T. Zeuch, G. Moréac, P. Dagaut, F. Mauss, On the implications of nitromethane – NO_x chemistry interactions for combustion processes, *Fuel* 289 (2021) 119861.
- A. Fomin, T. Zaylev, V.A. Alekseev, I. Rahinov, S. Cheskis, A.A. Konnov, Experimental and modelling study of 1CH₂ in premixed very rich methane flames, *Combust. Flame* 171 (2016) 198–210.
- P. Glarborg, A.B. Bendtsen, J.A. Miller, Nitromethane dissociation: implications for the CH₃+NO₂ reaction, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.* 31 (1999) 591–602.
- A.A. Konnov, Implementation of the NCN pathway of prompt-NO formation in the detailed reaction mechanism, *Combust. Flame* 156 (2009) 2093–2105.
- Y. Chan, F. Barnes, J. Bromly, A. Konnov, D. Zhang, The differentiated effect of NO and NO₂ in promoting methane oxidation, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 33 (2011) 441–447.

- [50] A.A. Konnov, J.N. Zhu, J.H. Bromly, D.-k. Zhang, The effect of NO and NO₂ on the partial oxidation of methane: experiments and modeling, *Proc. Combust. Inst* 30 (2005) 1093–1100.
- [51] A.A. Konnov, J. Chen, M. Lubrano Lavadera, Measurements of the laminar burning velocities of 1,2-butadiene: a comparative study, *Proc. Combust. Inst* 40 (2024) 105573.
- [52] A. Zubairova, J. Chen, A.A. Konnov, C. Brackmann, Flame structure study of premixed NH₃/O₂/Ar flames using Raman spectroscopy, *Combust. Flame* (under revis.) (2025).
- [53] E. Goos, A. Burcat, B. Ruscic, Ideal gas thermochemical database with updates from active thermochemical tables, April, <ftp://ftp.technion.ac.il/pub/supported/aetdd/thermodynamics/>, 2006. April.
- [54] D.G. Goodwin, R.L. Speth, H.K. Moffat, B.W.J.Z. Weber, Cantera: an object-oriented software toolkit for chemical kinetics, thermodynamics, and transport processes. <https://www.cantera.org> (accessed March 23, 2025). 10.5281/zenodo.6387882.
- [55] S. Wang, Z. Wang, A.M. Elbaz, X. Han, Y. He, M. Costa, A.A. Konnov, W.L. Roberts, Experimental study and kinetic analysis of the laminar burning velocity of NH₃/syngas/air, NH₃/CO/air and NH₃/H₂/air premixed flames at elevated pressures, *Combust. Flame* 221 (2020) 270–287.
- [56] S.J. Klippenstein, C.R. Mulvihill, P. Glarborg, Theoretical kinetics predictions for reactions on the NH(2)O potential energy surface, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 127 (2023) 8650–8662.
- [57] Y. Li, S.M. Sarathy, Probing hydrogen–nitrogen chemistry: a theoretical study of important reactions in N_xH_y, HCN and HNCO oxidation, *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 45 (2020) 23624–23637.
- [58] S.J. Klippenstein, L.B. Harding, P. Glarborg, J.A. Miller, The role of NNH in NO formation and control, *Combust. Flame* 158 (2011) 774–789.